

EUROFLEETS⁺ Floating University

Modern techniques and platforms for ocean observations”

Onboard the R/V Svea (and almost on R/V Skagerak)

Lysekil, Sweden 24-28 October 2022

Scientific Participants

Niklas Andersson (Course leader, UGOT)

Sebastiaan Swart (Teacher, UGOT)

Marcel Du Plessis (Teacher, UGOT)

Estel Font Felez (Teacher, UGOT)

Johan Edholm (Teacher, UGOT)

Bastien Queste (Teacher, UGOT)

Louise Biddle (Teacher UGOT, VOTO)

Ola Kalén (Teacher, SMHI)

Örjan Bäck (On board teacher, SMHI)

Martin Hansson (On board teacher, SMHI)

Björn Lindell (Teacher, SLU)

Nimal Sudhan Saravana Prabahar (Student, Sweden)

Kai Salm (Student, Estonia)

Loizos Groutas (Student, Cyprus)

Sarah Rautenbach (Student, Portugal)

Viviana Belvisi (Student, Portugal)

Yaomei Wang (Student, UK)

Ivia Closset (Student, France)

Fernando Segio Gois Smith (Student, Italy)

Cem Serimozu (Student, Turkey)

Eurofleets+ Floating University

Course and cruise objectives

Eurofleets+ Floating University

This international Eurofleets course exposed the participants to several state-of-the-art ocean observing platforms available in West Sweden. Training aspects include understanding of ship- and robotic-based observing techniques and their associated sensors and measurement capabilities. The course will provide ship time and to deployment of autonomous platforms. Participants Learned about instrument and platform deployments, robotic-platform piloting, to gain understanding of how different platforms collect data and through data processing and visualization, investigate which platforms are best to use for various scientific questions.

The course started with background lectures on the available infrastructure and instrumentation, the scientific rationale, the physical conditions and cruise planning. A glider was deployed in the end of the first day using smaller vessels and the first data from it was presented and processed the day after.

Two days was spent on board RV Svea for data collection with CTD, ADCP, MVP and Ferrybox. The data was then handled in smaller workshop and presented as a group project.

The learning objectives of the course were to:

- *Better understand modern techniques and platforms to collect ocean observations*
- *Go to sea on short research voyages to collect their own observations and deploy/recover instruments*
- *Better understand which types of platforms (e.g. ship vs glider) are suited to make the required measurements/survey*
- *Better understand how certain platforms and instruments function/are controlled remotely*
- *Plot and visualize near-real time data and data type comparisons, including data quality control*
- *Be exposed to examples of how such techniques and data are used in science/monitoring*

SHIPS

RV Svea, <https://www.slu.se/rv-svea>

The students

Nimal Sudhan Saravana Prabahar (University of Gothenburg, Sweden)

Kai Salm (Tallinn Institute of Technology, Estonia)

Loizos Groutas (University of Nicosia, Cyprus)

Sarah Rautenbach (CCMAR, Portugal)

Viviana Belvisi (University of Lisbon, Portugal)

Yaomei Wang (National Oceanography Center, UK)

Ivia Closset (Finnish Meteorological Institute, Finland)

Fernando Segio Gois Smith (Università Degli Studi di Firenze, Italy)

Cem Serimozu (Middle East Technical University, Turkey)

Nature of the course and work carried out on the course

The course was initially designed by a group of teachers, technicians, and researchers at the University of Gothenburg. A draft idea of the course content was already written in the Eurofleets+ grant agreement and with that as a base and the research interests of the available scientists at UGOT we formed an initial plan.

We then had several meetings with RV Svea operators and researchers at the Swedish Agricultural University SLU and the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrographical Institute SMHI to broaden the scope of the course.

The UGOT, SLU and SMHI group decided that one or two days of lectures about the hydrographical and physical background of the area, the capabilities of the vessels, the science available to research with the available equipment and the capabilities and limitations of different platforms was needed.

The students were given the task of being “trainee cruise leader” making them responsible for the on-board activities.

The limited time of the course made the UGOT, SLU, SMHI take the decision that no course report was needed. It was sufficient that the students made presentations and actively participated in a discussion on the last day of the course.

Course and cruise Log

Write a log of the activities carried out day by day

1st day (24 October 2022) – Kristineberg Marine Research Station

Description of activities: Introduction to participants, teachers, course outline and objectives. Scientific background to geographical area, scientific field, available instrumentation, platforms and research vessels.

Glider deployment from small boats.

2nd day (25 October 2022) – Kristineberg Marine Research Station

Description of activities: Continued scientific background. Cruise planning. Starting to look at glider data. Start of discussion on advantages and disadvantages of different platforms.

3rd day (26 October 2022) – RV Svea

Description of activities: Safety briefing on research vessel. On board lectures on equipment. Measurements with Ferrybox, ADCP, CTD and MVP.

4th day (27 October 2022) – RV Svea

Description of activities: Continued measurements with Ferrybox, ADCP, CTD and MVP. Glider recovery with RV Svea’s working boat. Looking at data. Preparing presentations.

5th day (28 October 2022) – *Kristineberg Marine Research station*

Description of activities: Preparing student's presentations. Presentation. Departure.

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On board operation

- Sampling methodology: MVP, CTD rosette; ADCP, Ferrybox and SeaExplorer glider

Preliminary results

The students found the data from MVP, CTD, ADCP and glider consistent.

The students saw the differences between different sampling methods and understood capabilities and limitations between research vessels and gliders and other autonomous platforms.

Their conclusion was that both research vessels and autonomous platforms are needed in the research of today and the future.

Evaluation of student learning

The students presented their work in a join oral presentation. Participants and evaluators were present both in the room and virtually. Each individual student had to show what they had learned during the week.

Students course evaluation

“Everything was PERFECT, so my suggestion is just to keep the same format. Everybody will probably suggest more time but, to be honest, the short time to make the decisions due to the deadlines was super important to push the group.”

„That structure and organization is key for efficient and continuous data acquisition. To see the redundancy of (meta)data documentation during the CTD casts was surprising and impressive at the same time. By doing so, it appears that the sampling can be reproduced on a regular base and that the data can be trusted as it was collected with so much care.“

„Platforms for marine observation have very distinct advantages and disadvantages. The lectures and the practical experience with them provided a good comparison of their strength and weaknesses.“

„The classes in the first two days were well structured, starting with some basic information about the Fjord and the surrounding environment as well as introductions into the different instruments. It was great that the cruise planning had to be done by the students and the teachers were there only to guide us. This experience was unfamiliar but was great to face that challenge together in a team.

The two days on Svea were sufficient to understand the instruments and the different deployments and data acquisition, which left us enough time after to process and interpret the data and putting it all together in a presentation.“

A very intensive course with lots of information in only 5 days. Students were happy with the opportunity to plan their own cruise and compare research vessels and autonomous platforms. The students wished the course was longer so they could get an even better understanding of the data.

Appendix

Agenda

Final presentation